

Synthesis of poly-styrene based nickel phosphate membrane : Evaluation of membrane parameters and to test the membrane potential theories

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Abstract : The fabrication of polystyrene-based nickel phosphate membranes at different pressures with varying amounts of material has been described. In order to understand the mechanism of transport of ions and to evaluate various membrane parameters controlling the transport phenomena, the membrane potential measurements were carried out using different concentrations of 1 : 1 electrolytes solutions. Teorell-Meyer and Sievers (TMS) method was used for the estimation of membrane parameter in the form of thermodynamically effective fixed charge density of membranes. The data were then utilized to calculate theoretical membrane potential values using extended TMS theory. Bi-ionic potential (BIP) measurements were reported keeping the same concentration of ionic species on the two sides of the membranes. On the other hand, Toyoshima and Nozaki method was used for the evaluation of theoretical values of bi-ionic potential (BIP) at the same concentration of ionic species on two sides of the membrane, utilizing the membrane parameters evaluated using the values of membrane potential. The close agreement between theoretical and observed values in both cases not only proved the existence of the membrane but also confirm the applicability to examine the validity of the theory utilized to the membrane electrolyte systems. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) monographs of the membrane have also been presented.

Keywords : Membrane potential, membrane bi-ionic potential, charge density, scanning electron microscope (SEM), polystyrene based nickel phosphate membrane.

Introduction

Membrane phenomena have been extensively studied with both natural and artificial membranes¹. In this paper, we describe the preparation of nickel phosphate membrane using different proportion of polystyrene as binder and by applying different pressures. The thermodynamically effective fixed charge density which is considered as the most effective parameter controlling the membrane phenomena, has been determined using the commonly used equation of Teorell, Meyer and Sievers (TMS)² from membrane potential measurements. The charge density, thus, derived have been used to calculate the theoretical membrane potential values at different electrolyte concentrations using the extended TMS theory³ and theoretical bi-ionic potential values with equations given⁴.

Results and discussion

Evaluation of membrane parameters and theoretical membrane potential : The values of membrane potential E_m , measured across polystyrene-based nickel phosphate membranes in contact with various 1 : 1 electrolytes at 25 ± 1 °C are given in Table 1. The values of membrane potential E_m , measured across the polystyrene based nickel phosphate membranes with 1 : 1 electrolytes (KCl, NaCl and LiCl) were dependent on the concentration of electrolytes present on both sides of the membrane at 25 ± 1 °C are given in Table 1. At higher concentrations, the potential was low. This is the usual behaviour of inorganic precipitate membrane⁵. The membrane potential is largely dependent on the pressure applied during the membrane formation. Higher pressure at the polystyrene based nickel phosphate membranes were caused to reduce in thickness,

Table 1. Observed membrane potential $E_m \pm 0.5$ mV across the polystyrene-based nickel phosphate membranes in contact with 1 : 1 electrolyte solution at different concentrations $C_2/C_1 = 10$ at 25 ± 1 °C

Concn. (C) (mol/L)	Applied pressure (t)														
	4			5			6			7			8		
	KCl	NaCl	LiCl	KCl	NaCl	LiCl	KCl	NaCl	LiCl	KCl	NaCl	LiCl	KCl	NaCl	LiCl
1×10^{-4}	50.0	50.5	52.0	51.0	52.0	53.0	52.0	54.0	55.0	53.0	54.0	56.0	54.0	55.0	57.5
5×10^{-4}	47.0	48.5	49.0	47.0	50.0	50.5	48.5	51.0	52.0	48.0	52.0	55.0	48.5	54.0	56.0
1×10^{-3}	44.0	47.0	48.0	45.0	47.0	49.0	46.0	49.5	50.5	47.0	50.0	54.0	48.0	53.0	55.0
5×10^{-3}	29.0	35.05	40.0	30.0	32.0	40.0	35.0	38.5	41.0	33.0	38.0	45.0	35.5	41.0	47.0
1×10^{-2}	23.0	30.0	33.0	25.0	29.0	35.0	26.0	32.0	35.0	27.0	34.0	40.0	30.0	40.0	44.0
5×10^{-2}	15.0	18.0	20.0	16.0	17.0	19.0	16.5	18.5	19.0	16.0	18.5	20.0	20.0	22.0	25.0
1×10^{-1}	12.0	13.0	16.0	13.0	14.0	15.0	14.5	16.0	17.0	15.0	16.0	18.0	18.0	20.5	22.0
1×10^0	10.0	11.5	13.0	10.5	11.0	12.0	12.0	13.5	15.0	12.5	14.0	15.5	15.5	17.0	18.0

contraction in pore volume increase in mechanical transport resistance and consequently offered a progressively higher fixed charge density⁶.

Inorganic precipitate membranes have the ability to generate potential⁷ when they are used to separate electrolyte solutions. The mobile species penetrate the membrane at different magnitude and various transport phenomena, including the development of potential across it, are induced into the system⁸. The nature of fixed charge in the membrane matrix greatly influences the counter ion than co-ion as well as the transport phenomena. The fixed charge concept for charged membrane² is a pertinent starting point for the investigations of the actual mechanisms of ionic or molecular processes which occur in membrane phase. These authors have derived the following equation for membrane potential E_m :

$$E_m = 59.2 \left(\log \frac{C_2}{C_1} \frac{\sqrt{4C_1^2 + \bar{X}^2} + \bar{X}}{\sqrt{4C_2^2 + \bar{X}^2} + \bar{X}} + \bar{U} \log \frac{\sqrt{4C_2^2 + \bar{X}^2} + \bar{X}\bar{U}}{\sqrt{4C_1^2 + \bar{X}^2} + \bar{X}\bar{U}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{U} = \frac{\bar{u} - \bar{v}}{\bar{u} + \bar{v}}$

where \bar{u} and \bar{v} are the ionic mobilities of cation and anion (m^2/vs), respectively, in the membrane phase. \bar{X} is the charge density expressed in equivalents per unit volume of membrane. To evaluate this parameter for the simple case of a 1 : 1 electrolyte and a membrane carrying a net negative charge of $\bar{X} = 1$ as well as $\bar{X} < 1$, theoretical concentration potentials E_m , existing across the membrane were calculated as a function of $-\log C_2$, the ratio C_2/C_1 being kept at a constant value of 10 for different mobility ratios \bar{u}/\bar{v} and plotted as shown by smooth curves in Fig. 2. The experimental curve was also plotted in the same figure. Thus, the coinciding theoretical curve gave the value for the charge density \bar{X} and the mobility ratio \bar{u}/\bar{v} within the membrane phase. The values of \bar{X} and \bar{u}/\bar{v} derived in this way for various membrane electrolyte systems are given in Table 2. The values of \bar{X} is found to depend on the applied pressure to which the membrane

was subjected to its initial stage of preparation. The microstructure of dense and loose aggregation of small particles of nickel phosphate membrane which form the interconnected channel and pore appeared to be more compact and arrange in order with successive increase in pressure can also be seen in the SEM and is presented in Fig. 1. The increase in the value of \bar{X} with higher applied pressure is due to successive increase of charge per unit volume as well as decrease in pore volume of nickel phosphate membrane and therefore, the degree of selectivity for ion is enhanced with the modification in surface microstructure of membrane.

Table 2. Derived values of membrane charge density ($\bar{X} \pm 0.1$) $\times 10^{-3}$ eq. (l) for nickel phosphate membrane electrolyte systems using TMS equation^a

Applied pressure (l)	Electrolyte (\bar{X})		
	KCl $\bar{X} \times 10^{-3}$	NaCl $\bar{X} \times 10^{-3}$	LiCl $\bar{X} \times 10^{-3}$
4	1.0	2.0	3.0
5	1.2	2.5	4.0
6	2.0	2.5	3.5
7	2.5	3.5	5.2
8	3.0	5.0	5.5

^aThe value of \bar{u}/\bar{v} as found to be 1.4.

In addition to the above equation, Teorell, Meyer and Sievers further extended their theory and derived another equation for membrane potential considering the total potential as the sum of Donnan potential E_{don} between the membrane surfaces and the external solutions, and the diffusion potential E_{diff} , within the membrane⁹,

$$E_{m.e.} = E_{don} + E_{diff} \quad (2)$$

where

$$E_{don} = - \frac{RT}{V_k F} \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_{\pm}^{\prime} C_2 \bar{C}_{1+}}{\gamma_{\pm}^{\prime} C_1 \bar{C}_{2+}} \right) \quad (3)$$

R , F and T have their usual significance, γ_{\pm}^{\prime} and $\gamma_{\pm}^{\prime\prime}$ are the mean ionic activity coefficients. \bar{C}_{1+} and \bar{C}_{2+} are the cation concentration on the two sides of the charged membrane and is given by the equation,

$$\bar{C}_{+} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{V_x \bar{X}}{2V_k} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\gamma_{\pm} C}{q} \right)^2} - \frac{V_x \bar{X}}{2V_k} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1. SEM images of polystyrene-based (25%) nickel phosphate membranes prepared at different applied pressures (P4T, P6T, P8T), respectively.

where V_k and V_x refer the valency of cation and fixed charge group on the membrane matrix, q is the charge effectiveness of the membrane and is defined by the equation,

$$q = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{\pm}}{K_{\pm}}} \tag{5}$$

where K_{\pm} is the distribution coefficient expressed as

$$K_{\pm} = \frac{\bar{C}_i}{C_i}, \bar{C}_i = C_i - \bar{X} \tag{6}$$

where \bar{C}_i is the i -th ion concentration in the membrane phase and C_i is the i -th ion concentration of the external solution. The diffusion potential E_{diff} was expressed in the form,

$$E_{diff} = -\frac{RT}{V_k F} \frac{\bar{\alpha}-1}{\bar{\omega}+1} \times \ln \left(\frac{(\bar{\omega}+1)\bar{C}_{2+} + (V_x/V_k)\bar{X}}{(\bar{\omega}+1)\bar{C}_{1+} + (V_x/V_k)\bar{X}} \right) \tag{7}$$

here $\bar{\omega} = \bar{u}/\bar{v}$ is the mobility ratio of the cation to anion in the membrane phase. The total membrane potential $E_{m,e}$ was, thus, obtained by simple addition of eqs. (3) and (7),

$$E_{m,e} = -\frac{RT}{V_k F} \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_{\pm}'' C_2 \bar{C}_{1+}}{\gamma_{\pm}' C_1 \bar{C}_{2+}} \right) - \frac{RT}{V_k F} \frac{\bar{\omega}-1}{\bar{\omega}+1} \times \ln \left(\frac{(\bar{\omega}+1)\bar{C}_{2+} + (V_x/V_k)\bar{X}}{(\bar{\omega}+1)\bar{C}_{1+} + (V_x/V_k)\bar{X}} \right) \tag{8}$$

In order to test the applicability of these theoretical equations for the system under investigation, the Donnan potential and diffusion potential were separately calculated from the membrane parameters obtained from membrane potential measurements using a typical membrane prepared at 6t pressure. Eqs. (9) and (10) were first used to get the values of transport numbers t_+ and t_- from experimental membrane potential data and consequently, the mobility ratio $\bar{\omega} = \bar{u}/\bar{v}$ within the membrane phase.

$$E_m = \frac{RT}{F} (t_+ - t_-) \ln \frac{C_2}{C_1} \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{\bar{u}}{\bar{v}} = \frac{t_+}{t_-} \tag{10}$$

The values of t_+ calculated from observed membrane potential are given in Table 3. Donnan potential at various electrolyte concentrations were then calculated from the parameters \bar{C}_{1+} , \bar{C}_{2+} , q' , q'' , K_{\pm}' and K_{\pm}'' and the experimentally derived values of charge density by using

Fig. 2. Plots of membranes potential vs $-\log C_2$ for nickel phosphate membranes prepared at different pressures 4–8t. Smooth curves are the theoretical concentration potentials for $\bar{X} = 1$ at different mobility ratio $\bar{u}/\bar{v}(1-4)$ and $\bar{X} < 1$ (5–11) and for $\bar{u}/\bar{v} = 1.4$. Broken lines are the experimental values of membrane potential E_m for different concentration of KCl solution.

Fig. 3. Membrane potential across nickel phosphate membrane using various 1 : 1 electrolyte solution at different concentrations. Solid lines are theoretical values obtained using eq. (8). Broken lines are experimental data.

eqs. (3)–(7). The values of the parameters derived for the systems have been given in Table 4. The values of γ_{\pm} were the usual charted values for electrolytes. The theoretical membrane potential derived and the

experimentally obtained membrane potentials at different concentrations for various electrolyte system have been compared and provided in Fig. 3. It may be noted that the experimental data follow the theoretical curve quite

well. However, some deviations may be due to various non-ideal effects, such as swelling effect and osmotic effects. These effects are often simultaneous present in the charged membranes.

Table 3. Transport number t_+ calculated from observed membrane potentials and using eq. (9) for various electrolyte concentrations with nickel phosphate membrane prepared at 6r pressure

Concn., C_2 (mol/L)	Electrolyte		
	KCl	NaCl	LiCl
1×10^{-4}	0.96	0.70	0.70
5×10^{-4}	0.68	0.69	0.69
1×10^{-3}	0.67	0.68	0.69
5×10^{-3}	0.62	0.64	0.65
1×10^{-2}	0.60	0.61	0.63
5×10^{-2}	0.56	0.57	0.57
1×10^{-1}	0.55	0.56	0.56
1×10^0	0.54	0.55	0.55

Evaluation of membrane parameters and theoretical bi-ionic (BIP) membrane potential : The steady state electromotive force of a cell containing two electrolytes separated by a membrane, called the bi-ionic potential (BIP), is a measure of selectivity of the membrane for the ions of the same sign. Various mathematically rigorous equations for BIP have been derived¹⁰. Toyoshima and Nozaki have derived an equation for membrane potential and bi-ionic potential using the principles of non-equilibrium thermodynamics utilizing approximate

Fig. 4. Plots of $1/t_+$ against $1/C_N''$ for various 1 : 1 electrolytes across nickel phosphate membrane.

assumptions for the mobilities and activity coefficients of small ions in the membrane phase⁴. The effect of ionic interaction, mass flow and osmotic effect were neglected. For a negatively charged membrane separating two 1 : 1 electrolytes (common co-ions) of the same concentration, these authors derived the following expression for bi-ionic potential,

$$E_{BIP} = [2 \ln (K_A/K_B) + \ln (JV_A + 1)/(JV_B + 1)] (F/RT) \quad (11)$$

Knowing the values of parameters K_A , K_B , V_A , V_B and the flux J , the values of theoretical E_{BIP} can be calculated using eq. (11). For the evaluation of these parameters, following equations have been suggested :

$$(2J + 1) \ln (g_A + 2J)/(g_B + 2J) - \ln (JV_A + 1)/(JV_B + 1) - \ln (g_A/g_B) = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\text{where } V_N = 1 + (VJ_N^0/V_P^0) \text{ and} \quad (13a)$$

$$g_N = 1 + [1 + (2K_N C/\bar{X})^2]^{1/2} [N = A, B] \quad (13b)$$

In order to derive the value of the parameter V_N and \bar{X} occurring in eqs. (13a) and (13b), Toyoshima and Nozaki⁴ derived an expanded and approximate eq. (14) for membrane potential E_m arising across a membrane when it is used to separate two solutions of an electrolyte at different concentrations C_N' and C_N''

Fig. 5. Plots of bi-ionic potential (BIP) against $\log c$ for various pairs of 1 : 1 electrolytes across nickel phosphate membrane.

Table 4. The calculated values of the parameter K_{\pm}^{\pm} , q' , \bar{C}_{2+} and $\bar{\omega}$ of nickel phosphate membrane with different concentration of electrolytes using eqs. (4)-(6), (9) and (10)

Concn., C_2 (mol/L)	Electrolyte													
	KCl			NaCl			LiCl			LiCl				
	K_{\pm}^{\pm}	q'	$\bar{\omega}$	K_{\pm}^{\pm}	q'	$\bar{\omega}$	K_{\pm}^{\pm}	q''	$\bar{\omega}$	K_{\pm}^{\pm}	q''	$\bar{\omega}$		
1×10^{-4}	4.359	0.479	0.0002	2.23	0.447	0.0002	4.900	0.447	0.0002	2.31	5.830	0.300	0.0003	2.35
1×10^{-3}	1.000	0.982	0.0010	2.02	0.802	0.0012	1.500	0.802	0.0012	2.09	2.500	0.621	0.0015	2.18
1×10^{-2}	0.800	1.061	0.0085	1.47	1.002	0.0090	0.750	1.002	0.0090	1.52	0.650	0.802	0.0096	1.69
1×10^{-1}	0.980	0.886	0.0869	1.24	0.888	0.0865	0.975	0.888	0.0865	1.27	0.965	0.893	0.0861	1.28
1×10^0	0.998	0.779	0.7777	1.19	0.779	0.7770	0.997	0.779	0.7770	1.22	0.9965	0.780	0.7770	1.24

$$(F/RT) E_m = - (1-2/V_N) \ln \gamma - 2(1-1/V_N) \bar{X} + (1/V_N) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma}\right) (\bar{X}/K_N) (1/C_N'') \quad (14)$$

The apparent transference number t_- for co-ion was defined by the Nernst equation

$$-(F/RT) E_m = (1 - 2t_-) \ln \gamma \quad (15)$$

Combining eqs. (14) and (15) and expanding $1/t_-$ as a power of series of C_N'' we obtain the following expression :

$$1/t_- = V_N + (V_N - 1) \left(\frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma \ln \gamma}\right) \left(\frac{\bar{X}}{K_N}\right) (1/C_N'') + \quad (16)$$

Eq. (14) predicts a linear relationship between $1/t_-$ and $1/C_N''$. The values of V_N and (\bar{X}/K_N) can be determined from the ordinate intercept and initial slope of a plot for $1/t_-$ against $1/C_N''$ shown in Fig. 4. The values of V_N and \bar{X}/K_N thus derived for the membrane and various 1 : 1 electrolyte systems are given in Table 5. The values of V_N and (\bar{X}/K_N) were then used to calculate J and g_N using eqs. (12) and (13). Once the membrane parameters V_N , g_N , J and (\bar{X}/K_N) are known for the membrane electrolyte systems, one can calculate the theoretical bi-ionic potential using eq. (11).

Table 5. Values of membrane parameters V_N and \bar{X}/K_N derived from the Toyoshima and Nozaki theory for polystyrene based nickel phosphate membrane

Electrolyte	V_N	\bar{X}/K_N
KCl	2.10	2.0×10^{-5}
NaCl	2.21	2.4×10^{-3}
LiCl	2.11	3.4×10^{-3}

In order to examine the validity of the recently developed membrane theories the theoretically derived values of membrane potential are shown by solid lines and experimentally observed values are shown by dotted lines in Fig. 3. Similarly, the derived theoretical bi-ionic potential (BIP) using eq. (11) and observed membrane bi-ionic potential values were plotted in Fig. 5 for their comparison. Figs. 3 and 5 show that the theoretical predictions were borne out quite satisfactorily by our

experimental results in both cases. However, the slight deviation in the values may be attributed to various reasons, most notably the various degrees of interaction of ions with the membrane. In addition to this, some deviations may be due to various non ideal effects like swelling and osmotic, hydrophobic/hydrophilic and specially membrane in homogeneity effects. These effect are often simultaneously present in charged membranes.

Experimental

Preparation of membrane :

Nickel phosphate precipitate was prepared by mixing a 0.2 M nickel(II) chloride with 0.2 M tri-sodium phosphate solution. The precipitate was washed well with deionized water to remove free electrolyte and dried at room temperature. The precipitate was ground into fine powder and was sieved through 200 mesh (granule size 0.07 mm). Pure amorphous polystyrene (cross linked with 1% divinylbenzene and obtain from Fluka, product number 81535) were also grounded and sieved. The membrane was prepared by the method as reported earlier^{5,11}. Different proportions of polystyrene and nickel phosphate precipitate were mixed thoroughly using grinder. The mixture was then kept into the cast die having diameter 2.45 cm and placed in an oven maintained at 200 °C for about half an hour to equilibrate. The die containing the mixture was then transferred swiftly to a pressure device (spectra Lab., Model SL 89, UK) and various pressures such as 4, 5, 6, 7 or 8t were applied during the formation of the membranes. As a result nickel phosphate membranes of approximate thickness 0.095, 0.090, 0.085, 0.080 and 0.075 cm were obtained, respectively. Our effort was to get the membrane of adequate chemical and mechanical stability. Thus, the membranes prepared by mixing 25% of polystyrene was found to be mechanically stable and was quite suitable for our studies. Those containing larger amount (>25%) of polystyrene did not give reproducible results, while those containing lesser amount (<25%) were unstable. The total amount of the mixture, thus, utilized for the preparation of the membrane contained 0.125 g of polystyrene and 0.375 g of nickel phosphate.

Measurement of membrane potential : The freshly prepared charged membrane were installed at the centre

of the measuring cell, which had two glass tubes, one on either side of the membrane. Both collared glass tubes contain hole for introducing the electrolyte solution and saturated calomel electrodes (SCE's). Electrochemical cell of the type

was constructed to measure membrane potential^{15,11} using Osaw vernier potentiometer (C. No. 30071, UK). In all measurements, $C_2/C_1 = 10$. The bi-ionic membrane potentials were measured by using the different electrolyte solution of same concentration across the membrane. All solutions were prepared by using analytically reagent (A.R.) grade chemicals and doubly distilled water. The pressure and temperature were kept constant throughout the experiment and potentials were measured at 25 ± 1 °C.

SEM investigation of membrane morphology : Recently, a number of investigators while developing precipitates/ membranes have frequently utilized scanning electron microscope (SEM) micrographs for their characterization¹². The composite pore structure, micro/macro porosity; homogeneity, thickness, cracks and surface texture/morphology have been specially studied by scanning electron microscopy¹³. The information obtained from microscopic photographs/images have provided guidance in the preparation of well ordered precipitates and/or crack-free membranes. Consequently, the SEM surface images of the nickel phosphate membranes were taken. These are presented in Fig. 1. SEM images appear to be composed of dense and loose aggregation of small particles and formed pores probably with non-linear channel but not fully interconnected. Particles are irregularly condensed and adopt a heterogeneous structure composed of masses of various size. The surface openings also seem to decrease with increasing applied pressure.

Conclusion : Membranes prepared at high pressure carry higher charge density and have narrow surface openings/channels. Charge density values obtained by the frequently used TMS procedures, have been used to test

the recently extended TMS equation by computing membrane potential at different concentrations. On the other hand these charge density values have also been used to test the bi-ionic potential theories by evaluating the membrane parameters and using them to calculate theoretical bi-ionic potential values.

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